

AI, Decomputing and the Interregnum

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Abstract

This paper treats AI as diagnostic for the deeper changes taking place in the existing order of things. It uses AI's alignment with both the political economy and with the dualisms that underpin it, including race, gender and anthropocentrism, to highlight the nihilistic character of the current restructuring. AI's scaling and accelerationism are taken as examples of the wider tactics being invoked by hegemonic power to maintain control under changing conditions. From this perspective, the massive build-out of data centres isn't simply a seizure of energy resources but a manifestation of an aggressive and misogynist technopolitics. The paper argues that a liberal push for digital sovereignty doesn't interrupt these dynamics but plays into the hands of emerging technofascism. It proposes instead the prefigurative tactic of 'decomputing', which draws on degrowth, deautomatisation and a convivial approach to technology. It explores decomputing as a means to mitigate both material and relational harms and as a decisive turn towards infrastructuring the common good. The paper concludes that AI is the contradiction that reveals many others, not least the gap between claims to legitimacy and the actuality of destructive violence, and proposes an alternative technopolitics of reciprocity that prioritises care and sustainability.

AI as we currently know it is a site of strategic contradictions. On the one hand, it continues to acquire immense strategic and financial commitments from governments, investors and industry. On the other, its functional shortcomings have been decisively exposed by a range of informed critics (Bender & Hanna, 2025; McQuillan, 2022). AI at its core is a mechanism of pattern matching and pattern generation based on mere correlations. When implemented as billions of parameters this can produce some very convincing simulations, but whether its extruding text or making predictions, AI is always faking it. The current set of computational techniques layered onto neural networks are inherently unreliable, reductive and harmful to any application involving the complexity of human relations. AI isn't even industrially productive (Goldman Sachs, 2024). Rather, the assemblage of technologies and narratives that constitutes the AI complex are the site of convergence for a number of powerful forces. This paper will explore these strategic contradictions as important symptoms of the current historical moment. Despite failing on its own terms, AI serves the real needs of those seeking to restructure the concentration of power by deepening authoritarianism and doubling down on fossil fuel and extractive energy politics. AI is worthy of urgent attention not because of its innate capacities but because of the

ways in which its very failings are a lens on nihilistic changes taking place in the existing order of things.

Alignments

It's important to be clear from the start what this paper means when referring to AI. On the one hand the term has become an empty signifier, and on the other the material apparatus has specific qualities which are germane to argument about its technopolitics. When I talk about the technical dimension of AI I'm referring to a specific mode of computation based on neural networks and transformer models, and when I refer to AI in general terms I'm also including the associated logics institutions, investments and claims. This kind of AI is clearly delivering on a set of short-term capitalist priorities. It enables employers to further precaritise workers (Merchant, 2025), it channels venture capital to oligarchs, and it provides governments with a way to 'fix' services without actually reversing austerity. However, the argument here is that AI's traction also rests on fundamental dualisms in our social conditioning. In this sense, all the noise from the advocates of so-called 'AI Safety' about the need for alignment with human values is completely specious because AI already aligns with the hierarchical binaries that shape society at the deepest levels, especially misogyny, racism and a contempt for nature. It's these deeper patterns, in addition to factors in the political economy, that make AI a diagnostic for a system undergoing radical change.

It's not simply that the AI field itself is male-dominated, or that image models show such facility for non-consensual pornography (Burgess, 2025), but that the framework of AI systemically devalues interrelationship and care. AI's calculations erase any embedded and embodied relationships that can't be captured by its extractive datafication, and its architectures elevate abstraction over context and utilitarian optimisation over a concern for shared vulnerabilities. This muscular approach chimes all too well with the armoured masculinity and misogyny that permeates society more widely (Bates, 2026). When machine learning systems preferentially pin accusations of fraud on racial minorities (Amnesty International, 2024) it not only reflects the prejudice of those setting the parameters but also the racialising character of computations that can only segregate through correlation and which completely ignore structural disadvantage. Draping AI in the scientific 'view from above' while severing it from any attempt to understand cause-and-effect also means it becomes a second-order distancing from nature. By requiring that the world be fully abstracted via its matrix optimisations, AI recapitulates the alienation that has enabled the profit-led extractivism of industrial capitalism and the externalisation of environmental consequences.

AI is, therefore, both an engine of the capitalist status quo and a model of the gender, race and anthropocentric dualisms that make it tick. When, as now, the status quo fractures in unpredictable ways, these entanglements become a way to diagnose the changes. The dimensions of the crisis that AI is being pressed into service to address are both geopolitical, with the breakdown of the neoliberal world order, and psychopolitical, with the unsettling of a hegemonic subjectivity based on patriarchal,

ethnic and anthropocentric foundations. However, like all forms of solutionism, the turn to AI is actually amplifying the underlying problems and injustices, and making them even more visible in the process. Rather than treating AI itself as the driver of structural transformation, its overt entanglements with wider material and political forces are a guide to what we can expect from the ongoing restructuring.

Interregnum

The narratives around AI present it as the herald of an endpoint, whether that's the arrival of superintelligent machines or a more transcendent Singularity, but it would be more accurate to interpret it as a technopolitics of the interregnum; that is, of the period of discontinuity and disruption between different world orders. AI has arisen during a period of global destabilisation and polycrisis, when it's unclear what kind of power structures will emerge to replace the previous system, and its role in amplifying the various crises can be seen in its connections to financial austerity, militarisation and climate change.

The first wave of applied deep learning came to the fore in the decade following the global financial crash, and its facility for algorithmic triage became immediately appealing to institutions driven by an agenda of austerity. AI's net effect on employment continues to be one of precarisation through its alleged ability to replace workers, although the apparent substitution of some activities by a substandard algorithmic simulations has mainly been used to legitimise arbitrary sackings at scale (Constantz & Mason, 2026). Meanwhile, the largest AI companies have publicly abandoned their previous commitments to the peaceful application of AI and cosied up to the military-industrial complex (O'Donnell, 2024). While a short term driver may be the bubble-like aspect of AI financing and a belief that military contracts will fill the gap, the militarisation of AI is also part of the rush by nation states to boost rearmament and prepare for conflict. The aspect of AI which continually sabotages its reliability in social settings, which is its innate tendency to generate collateral damage through out-of-distribution errors (where the real-life scenario was missing from the training data) and so-called hallucinations ceases to be a problem in conflicts where maximum indiscriminate damage is the actual point (Abraham, 2023). The other claim that AI companies have recently abandoned is the goal of net zero carbon emissions. Until the advent of generative AI, the big tech companies were able to perform a level of corporate greenwashing through carbon offsets and by using their purchasing power to monopolise available sources of renewable energy. The strategic push for victory in LLMs and similar tech has locked them into to such an accelerating curve of data centre construction that the companies have publicly abandoned any aspiration to carbon neutrality (Rahman-Jones, 2024; Rathi & Bass, 2024).

As Antonio Gramsci so aptly put it, "The crisis consists precisely in the fact that the old is dying and the new cannot be born; in this interregnum a great variety of morbid symptoms appear" (Gramsci, 1996). AI's boosters would have us believe that AI is the future, and this future will be characterised by unlimited productivity and the end of disease. However, despite their genuinely impressive facility for simulating

interactivity and intelligence, these technologies continually trip over their own feet by making extremely obvious their lack of world understanding or even common sense. Rather than waxing lyrical about tech utopias, it is more useful to ask what AI's symptoms can tell us about the direction of travel of hegemonic power in these uncertain times.

One aspect of AI that has marked its development since the initial deep learning breakthroughs has been the necessity of scale. While AlexNet, the convolutional neural network whose sudden advance in image classification sparked the turn to contemporary AI, had about sixty million trainable parameters, leading edge LLMs are now of the order of hundreds of billions of parameters (Sevilla et al., 2024). The industry is locked into scale as the driver of improved performance on key metrics, whether that's through increasing model size or multiplying amounts of inference. The first thing that the faith in scale reflects about the wider restructuring is that it will still be founded on the principle of growth. Scaling is the AI industry's version of continuous growth, which is itself the non-negotiable feature of capitalism. The fundamental need for growth is visible in the centrality of GDP as a measure of economic performance, a reductive quantification which makes no distinction between activities which are helpful or harmful to general human wellbeing. AI scaling has a similarly sociopathic focus on performance metrics that pays no attention to the social or environmental impacts of the whole exercise. The other symptom to note about AI is its accelerationism (Andreessen, 2023). AI hype is the textbook expression of a belief that we should go further and faster, that our existing mechanisms should be overclocked to the point of meltdown in order to break through whatever barriers are holding us back, so we can transition to a new era. Accelerationism is a profoundly reactionary movement which is prepared to sacrifice ordinary lives and livelihoods in pursuit of its totalising vision. Its implications are already visible in the deranged ambitions of Silicon Valley oligarchs and in the convergence between Big Tech and MAGA politics.

While AI's actual operations coincide with fissures in the existing order of things, it also points to ways in which the same system seeks to re-order itself to maintain control. Despite AI's failure to be the next all-powerful technology, the associated scaling and accelerationism are indicators of the nihilistic tactics being adopted by hegemonic power.

Energetics

The commitments of large AI companies to a green future was always hypocritical at best. Even when Microsoft, for example, was claiming to pursue net zero as a corporation, it was simultaneously soliciting business from oil companies with the promise that AI could identify new oil reserves with unprecedented efficiency (Microsoft News Center, 2018). Nevertheless, AI corporations benefited for years from the aura of tech as an innately progressive force. This has all changed with the acceleration in data centre build-out. The utter materiality of AI, which had been obscured for years by discourses of abstraction, has elbowed its way back into public consciousness because of the sheer scale of the demand for land, water and energy. The

logics of AI have led to the construction of concrete cathedrals of computation that house thousands of high-end GPU microprocessors and which require corresponding volumes of electrical power and cooling water. Commissioning these data centres has become core to the AI project, meaning that more communities around the world are required to accommodate installations that stress local electricity supplies and water tables. Data centres are sited in a way that punches downwards, whether that's xAI's Colossus dumping its air pollution across neighbouring and historically deprived Black communities (Brabenec, 2025), or AI companies taking advantage of negotiating power with Global South governments to force their build-out into areas that can least absorb them, such as the Santiago metropolitan area during its ongoing and decades-long drought (Urquieta & Dib, 2024). AI's infrastructures are textbook examples of environmental injustice.

The energy demands of data centres are putting such a strain on ageing electricity grids that power cuts are becoming almost inevitable. Even so, the supply can't keep up and data centres are increasingly turning to gas turbines as a temporary or permanent power fix, boosting carbon emissions and polluting the air for local people (Pandey et al., 2025). The visible and naked sacrifice of community interests for AI has led to the risk of a backlash in the USA itself, to the extent that the industry has switched PR tactics from greenwashing to data centre washing (Edwards, 2026). It hasn't helped that other aspects of infrastructural logics, ranging from tax breaks and land prices to the need to cluster near internet backbones, have led to these data centres appearing in places that are least well placed to absorb their demands. Whether its data centres in areas of desertification or drought, or moratoriums on urban house building because data centres have already bought up the available grid supply, AI infrastructure is increasingly pitting itself against local people.

The driver of data centre expansion isn't simply the scale of computing required to hit the next market-leading metric but the momentum that has built up behind AI as the solution to social, political and environmental crises. AI has become a strategic matter as well as commercial one. Data centre mega-projects, like OpenAI's Stargate, are launched as part of 'making America great' as well as inevitable steps on the road to AGI. Meanwhile, the build-out itself has become self-reinforcing, as a massively investable activity in global markets that are otherwise stagnating. It's particularly notable that the AI companies no longer boast about their latest data centres in terms of the computation they will provide but by the scale of their energy demands in megawatts and gigawatts. The level of energy required has itself become a key proxy for power and success.

AI's resource demands are a lens on the repositioning of powerful actors to maintain the concentration of control under changed conditions. The process resembles Ernst Jünger's concept of 'total mobilisation'; the channelling of the entire material and energy resources of a nation into a new technological order based on the vitalism of conflict (McQuillan, 2026). The spectacle of the so-called 'AI Wars', the struggle for global AI dominance between the superpowers of the USA and China, is a symptom of a wider contest for the geopolitical seizure of global supply chains. The Great Powers are as unsure as anyone else about the way things will pan out and are seeking control of AI and so-called green technologies as well as reaffirming their

supply of fossil fuels. Attention to AI's energy entanglements is a window on systemic restructuring that, in pragmatic terms, acknowledges the fact of climate change and failure of neoliberalism, but seeks to navigate this in ways that maintain the power of domestic elites. This involves the collaboration of state and corporate actors in pushing for geopolitical control over strategic network dependencies (Alami, 2025). The current US regime has given its own efforts the title of Pax Silica ("Pax Silica," n.d.), in reference to Imperial Rome's claim to stability through hegemonic power and regional expansion. This kind of 'imperial state capitalism' hasn't simply opened the floodgates for the massive and visible profiteering of tech corporations but has led to their alignment with openly authoritarian politics.

Sovereignty

The renewed push for raw imperialism, as highlighted by AI, is causing a level of panic in other national governments. The public admission by Canada's Prime Minister, a died-in-the-wool neoliberal, that the previous 'international rules-based order' had always been a cover for US hegemony (Carney, 2026) indicates the degree of splintering going on. In terms of tech, this alarm has led to the emergence of a narrative of 'AI sovereignty', which has a woolly definition but indicates AI under national or European control. Calls for sovereign AI have generated widespread momentum by tapping into concerns about the growing harms of AI in everyday life, given the way these technologies are mostly controlled by Silicon Valley and a few Chinese corporations. However, the push for AI sovereignty doesn't do anything to address the underlying issues. A European or national AI is no more able to deliver on its claims than the existing models, while indicating the same commitment to growth at the expense of communities and the environment. Bringing AI under the jurisdiction of national law, if that was even possible, doesn't guarantee a just transition, and the law is also capable of being mystifying technology. It's not as if scattering flag-flying data centres over the homeland is going to fix AI's functional failings

In fact, the nationalist drive for AI sits happily alongside the wider dynamics of militarisation, authoritarian austerity and climate change solutionism. Most fundamentally, sovereign AI does nothing to address the underlying social dualisms of race, gender and nature; rather, it intensifies them.

What's happening with AI sovereignty is an instance of the wider dynamic where existing power structures look to retain control under rapidly changing circumstances. Switching from Big Tech to Brit Tech, for example, simply puts the toxic cocktail of AI in the hands of UK oligarchs rather than US or Chinese tech giants. In addition, the push for sovereign AI stokes the rising tide of far right populism. It aligns with a retreat to the certainty of a patriarchal order, guaranteed by a 'them and us' approach to national identity. Taking AI as a diagnostic in this case means an interrogation not only of sovereignty as national authority but of 'power over' as such, and the subjectivity that desires it. What AI has made increasingly and irretrievably visible is the aggressive masculine and supremacist culture of Big Tech, a stance it shares with authoritarian politics. The patriarchal personhood that is trying to reclaim what it feels as its natural right is a type of 'autogenetic sovereignty'; the

self-production of an armoured selfhood with no vulnerabilities or dependencies that deals with any challenge through an escalation of force (Bratich, 2022). Under conditions of crisis and collapse, where people feel cheated of their chance to occupy that power, narratives of misogyny and patriotic nationalism find fertile ground. In the end, arguments for AI sovereignty repeat the pattern of historical fascism; an appeal to popular discontent couched in terms of an external threat, combined with a concentration of elite power (Paxton, 2005). The notion of sovereign AI is a symptom of the transition from AI as automated neoliberalism to AI as an apparatus of fascisation (moving in the direction of fascism).

Technofascism

Like classical and contemporary fascisms, the AI apparatus is both demonstrably stupid and capable of shocking violence. As the restructuring moves further towards authoritarianism, these potentials are increasingly actualised. Arguments based on reason, for example that systems don't work properly or identify the wrong people, are misconceived because the cruelty is the point. Under nihilistic conditions, the threatened subject doesn't hope for salvation as such but merely wishes to see the Other suffer more than them. It's notable that the most widespread use of machine learning by governments in Europe is to generate accusations of welfare fraud, and it was similar allegations that legitimised deploying Immigration and Customs Enforcement (ICE) into the Somali communities of Minneapolis and the open murder of people trying to monitor them (Hogan, 2026). The technological apparatus of AI may be more-or-less useless for social reproduction, but it has some very desirable features for those who want to create a machine for mass deportation or other forms of ethnic cleansing.

AI is also shedding light on the neo-religious belief systems that energise significant parts of its milieu. The thread that runs through ideologies like transhumanism and Effective Altruism is broadly eschatological; the expectation of the end of the present age and a profound transformation that comes after that moment of singularity. This is so clearly articulated in statements from the founders and funders of major AI enterprises about the imminence of Artificial General Intelligence that it needs no further diagnosis or interpretation. However, it has spawned political currents which are less visible and more diffuse, and carry their conviction about the absolute priority of AI accelerationism into policy circles and political decision-making (Bordelon, 2024). These influence both the capital-accumulating hype around AI itself and the strategic commitments to AI as a solution to apocalyptic crises. What they always carry with them is a set of eugenicist predispositions about what kinds of sacrifice are acceptable, and for whom, in order to reach the promised redemption. It should be pointed out, of course, that algorithmic eugenics at home also means intensified colonial repression at the periphery, where the necropolitics never went away (Ali, 2019).

While these elitist belief systems are profoundly dangerous for the rest of us, the advent of AI also highlights the difficulty of doing something to restrain them without falling back into the same patterns. Bemoaning the capture by Big Tech of democratic

institutions and regulatory mechanisms is fair on one level but fatally overlooks the underlying continuities. As critics of the Enlightenment have pointed out, the secularisation of society that replaced the divine right of kings with representative democracy didn't completely dispense with the idea of sacred authority, but rather reinvested it in concepts of constitution and the sovereign power of the State (Newman, 2017). In other words, resisting forms of technofascism enabled by a belief in the transcendent power of technology are going to be undermined by appeals to the transcendent power of the State. The abstraction and alienation from our own agency that is so visible with AI is an echo of the abstraction and alienation already present in our existing political structures. The repeated refrain from liberal standpoints that the only reasonable response to the threats from AI is to rely on our established forms of governance is already a visible failure and will continue to be so.

The Epstein scandal is possibly the most visceral evidence of the inescapable corruption and misogyny of current power structures. AI is directly entangled with Epstein through the participation of leading Silicon Valley figures such as Zuckerberg, Musk and Gates in Epstein's influence-trading, and in his funding of research initiatives (Ahmed, 2025). Through his own supremacist beliefs and through relationships with people like Steve Bannon, Epstein personifies the bridge between the tech elite and the fascist politics of MAGA. Above all, the revelations about Epstein are a figure for the blatantly misogynist and unrestrained power that circulates through hegemonic elites for whom the lives of ordinary people are distant unrealities. The convictions of entitlement and superiority that are so evident here are built on the same binaries of race, gender and anthropocentrism that AI leans on for its own aura of worldly power and efficacy. The AI industry is a concentrated network of masculine power which enables an apparatus of widespread abuse. In a fundamental sense, AI is Epstein Tech, and whatever comes after it will be as well unless we find ways to radically redefine our approach to technopolitics.

Decomputing

This paper has characterised AI as a diagnostic of ongoing systemic crisis and restructuring. The form of the restructuring is essentially nihilist neoliberalism, or what we might call nihiloliberalism, in that it intensifies the dynamic of endless growth while doubling down on hierarchies of oppression that enable it. AI is a form of futuring whose claims to inevitability try to bring dystopia into the present. The response proposed here tackles technology as the convergence of politics and subjectivity; in other words, as raising the question of what kind of society we want to live in and who we need to be in order to inhabit that society. It attempts to distill from the disastrous turn to AI a number of ways to arrest accelerationism and open up the possibility of alternative technological futures. The term that will be used here for this approach is 'decomputing'.

Decomputing marshals a set of approaches rooted in existing social movements and historical technopolitics. It focuses in particular on degrowth, deautomatisation, care and conviviality. Decomputing recognises that technologies like AI are forms of futuring, in that the claim to inevitability attempts to bring very specific futures into

the present. Decomputing is therefore a prefigurative approach (Monticelli, 2024). It acknowledges that, for the reasons already outlined in this paper, existing systems of representational politics are demonstrably unable to contain the social violence of AI and the forces behind it. Rather than proposing representations of a better society that rely on these same mechanisms for their realisation, decomputing tries to tackle technopolitics in the here-and-now in ways that are consistent with preferred futures and that stand at least some chance of iterating towards them.

The first pillar of decomputing is degrowth (Schmelzer et al., 2022). AI's runaway scaling is the latest instance of a centuries-long commitment to endless expansion and extraction. The need to change direction has been clear in the Western canon since at least the Limits to Growth report from the early seventies (Meadows et al., 2018). Moreover, indigenous peoples have consistently warned that a civilisational drive to burn through the very fabric of ecological interdependence will end badly for everyone. A central goal of degrowth is to remove this systemic drive for imperialist expansion. As degrowth is a direct challenge to the core operations of capitalism and neoliberalism, there has been a sustained campaign to discredit it (McAleenan, 2020). However, in the context of the intensifying global polycrisis, the principles of degrowth come across as a relatively modest set of minimum demands. It is simply the proposition that we need a democratic transition to a society with a smaller throughput of energy and resources. This isn't a call for universal austerity - austerity is, after all, something that has been delivered by the unjust concentrations of wealth and power in our existing economy. Rather, it is a form of rebalancing that aims for social and ecological justice, on the basis that this gives everyone a better chance of a life worth living and a world in which we can continue to live those lives. AI is the acid test here because it is explicitly based on sharply increasing the throughput of energy and resources, and on doing so in ways that intensify injustice. If we are to construct a technopolitics consistent with degrowth, it will need to stand in sharp contrast to contemporary AI. Fortunately, the question of a more sustainable approach to computing is one that is already a matter of active investigation under headings like 'frugal computing' (Vanderbauwhede, 2023), 'slow computing' and 'computing within limits' (Nardi et al., 2018). The aim of decomputing is to combine this with a destituent approach to political power; that is, with an approach that denies legitimacy to any form of order based on automatisisation.

The second pillar of decomputing is therefore deautomatisation. As this paper has argued, AI draws power from connecting to the underlying divisions which structure both society and our psyches. It's not simply that AI's outputs are racist (Hofmann et al., 2024), sexist (Kapoor & Narayanan, 2025) and so on, but that AI brings a machinic amplification to binaries of power through scale, opacity and the distancing of human relationships. AI's normative effect on the conditions of thought reduces the capacity for autonomy and rewards reactions that reflect social hierarchies. Clearly, altering or even abolishing the application of certain algorithms won't remove the thoughtlessness and social resentment that accompanies them, but it does at least recognise their algorithmic amplification. Prefigurative action to dismantle AI violence means working at the same time on the violence that continuously expresses itself in microsocial interactions and institutional cruelties. One focus of

decomputing, therefore, is on the formation of assemblies and collectivities such as workers' and people's councils. Such forms of self-organisation are deautomatising, inasmuch as they are founded on peer-to-peer relationships and directly democratic processes. Collective struggle under conditions of consensus and trust is a way to push back against the repetition of inherited social patterns. Likewise, the act of care is the antithesis to armoured subjectivities, because it rehumanises us for each other and creates the conditions for empathy, itself described by tech oligarch Elon Musk as 'the fundamental weakness of Western Civilisation' (Wolf, 2025). Workers' and people's councils are ways of caring about each other and about our shared futures at the same time. Care underpins the possibility of an alternative restructuring, as the activity of sustaining bodies, selves and environments as part of a complex and ecological web (Tronto, 2019). By opposing the logics of automation and arguing for the fundamental importance of self-organised care, deautomation is a fundamentally constructive activity that works to establish situatedness and relations-in-place.

The third pillar of decomputing is conviviality, in particular the approach to convivial tools espoused by Ivan Illich. His definition of tool accommodates both technologies and institutional structures: "I use the term 'tool' broadly enough to include not only simple hardware such as drills, pots, syringes, brooms, building elements, or motors, and not just large machines like cars or power stations; I also include among tools productive institutions such as factories that produce tangible commodities like corn flakes or electric current, and productive systems for intangible commodities such as those which produce 'education,' 'health,' 'knowledge,' or 'decisions.'" (Illich, 1975). A convivial approach to technology is one that puts tools back in their place as extensions of explicitly social goals. Decomputing takes advantage of efforts to define specific criteria for deciding whether technical developments are convivial, such as the Matrix of Convivial Technologies (Vetter, 2018). This lays out a structured way for any group developing or adopting a technology to ask questions about key aspects of it, such as relatedness (how does it affect relations between people?) and bio-interaction (how does the tech interact with living organisms and ecologies?). This approach is directly applicable to the goal of deautomation, as Illich's stated purpose in *Tools for Conviviality* was "to lay down criteria by which the manipulation of people for the sake of their tools can be immediately recognized". He proposed the concept of counterfoil research as a way to tackle the kind of obsessive focus on the refinement of thoughtless mechanism which is so visible in the AI industry. As he put it; "Counterfoil research has two major tasks: to provide guidelines for detecting the incipient stages of murderous logic in a tool; and to devise tools and tool-systems that optimize the balance of life, thereby maximizing liberty for all." In short, convivial tools are those that minimise the potential for fascistic application and maximise the affordances for sustainable futures.

Decomputing is less of a programme or a set of steps, and more a framework for escalation. By bringing together degrowth, deautomation and conviviality, decomputing aims to be a framework for disrupting technofascism and for infrastructuring the common good.

Infrastructuring the Common Good

We can take data centres and their rapacious demand for resources as one place to start developing a practice of decomputing. The imposition of an AI data centre on a community brings immediate reasons for resistance, especially in relation to the amount of electricity they consume. We've seen that this can mean a variety of harms for communities, from overloading the local grid to increased energy bills, to immersion in air pollution from the gas turbines which are installed as data centre's own 'behind the meter' supply. Issues caused by the water consumption of the data centres and their need to cool tens of thousands of GPU chips are intensified when, as so often seems to be the case, these gargantuan buildings are sited in areas of existing water stress. A growing awareness of these very material implications is driving grass roots resistance to data centres (Barakat, 2025). A refusal of data centre construction is clearly in line with decomputing, as these infrastructures fail any assessment of conviviality and clearly play into the agenda of accelerating growth. Resisting data centres can also be an example of what we might call 'infrastructural intersectionality', of recognising that these material structures drive overlapping social harms. The communities having hyperscale data centres foisted on them are also likely to figure in jobs where the exploitation is directly algorithmic, whether that's in Amazon warehouses, as gig workers or as outsourced data labourers. They may also be from social demographics subjected to AI-powered targeting for welfare fraud or deportation. Infrastructural intersectionality calls attention to the potential for political solidarity in the face of a spectrum of AI harms, and recognises these as products of underlying structural factors. These are the conditions from which people's councils and similar kinds of assembly can emerge, as the self-organisation of local people in the face of institutional complicity by local administrations.

However, it turns out that a successful campaign against a particular data centre might just defer the problem until the corporation tries again, or might translate it to somewhere less able to resist. Resource theft by data centres is also, therefore, a catalyst for systemic transition. The current attention on the environmental harms of data centres actually poses the question of how to re-socialise all of society's energy and water resources. It's not simply that the data centre is expropriating the energy and water, but that the privatised utilities that resulted from the decades of neoliberalism are only too happy to play along. It's not simply that the financial might of Big Tech can claim control over common good resources, but that governments obsessed with GDP growth are willing to let them do it. More than simply demanding re-nationalisation, models like socialisation (Schmidt et al., 2024) shows us how the public ownership of a resource isn't an end in itself but can be the first step in developing collective and directly democratic planning. The social management of electricity and water, and of other goods like housing, are not blindingly new ideas but a matter of dusting off various arrangements that have been proposed in the past (Blumenfeld, 2023). While this might feel like a paradigm shift for those of us subjectivised by the long decades of neoliberalism, a mutual and layered governance of common goods at local, regional and even international level is not only conceivable but considerably less complex than the tech we're placing our trust in to solve our existing problems, and considerably more likely than any dreams of

emergent machine intelligence bringing us into a fully automated utopia.

Of course, such a transition is anathema to existing stakeholders, and decomputing advocates direct action where possible to manifest prefigurative change and to pile on the pressure for wider transformations. In terms of electricity supply, for example, there are already varieties of community energy co-ops and infrastructure, some of which have emerged from conditions of collapse. In the face of effective state abandonment of Puerto Rico in the aftermath of Hurricane Maria in 2017, some citizens of the island determined that the way to contest their relative disposability was to develop a decentralised solar energy grid under community control. While still small-scale, it was the solar panel installations of Casa Pueblo, run by local community organisers, that managed to sustain people in the face of another hurricane five years later (Espada, 2022). Similar climactic events also provide examples of self-organised infrastructures of care. In the immediate aftermath of Hurricane Sandy hitting New York, groups associated with the previous year's Occupy Movement established an effective mutual aid operation to distribute aid and provide urgent support. By combining logistics and on-the-ground outreach, this managed to get aid to many people neglected by the reluctant and racist state-led effort (Greenfield, 2024). One notable aspect is that the help provided by Occupy Sandy wasn't dependent on any attempt to classify or rank people according to institutional boundaries of deserving or undeserving, or to assess their eligibility according to some criteria of citizenship. People in need were treated as the peers of those coming to help, on the basis of commonality. Both of these examples also open the question of which kinds of limited or frugal computing could support and extend such efforts in convivial ways. The goal of decomputing is to deactivate existing apparatuses of computational power and return to common use the technical means for making our own arrangements. Initiatives for infrastructuring the common good will become ever more important as the consequences of the polycrisis play out, whether that's as climate events or in the increasingly violent paroxysms of the political-economy collapsing in on itself.

Prefiguration

A refusal of AI is a forensic approach to finding out what has already gone wrong in any situation where AI is proposed as a solution. Closely examining the context will reveal the forms of reductive quantification and relational automatism that have decimated the ground in advance, from the technocratic metricisation of education to the austerity-driven triage of social provision. AI simply extends the twin agendas of capital accumulation and control. Decomputing is a call to reestablish the primacy of relationship and reciprocity in any of these settings, and to prioritise social needs over profit. As discussed, one mechanism it proposes for this purpose are workers' and people's councils, as these are exercises in critical pedagogy, of learning together about situated problems and about what needs to be done, and in the development of counter-power. The logic of the assembly emerges in situations where people realise they can't rely on whichever institution or sovereign force claims legitimacy over a particular issue. The time is ripe for such experiments in structured mutuality, as existing forms of hegemonic authority are leaking legitimacy faster than new forms of computational distraction can be produced. Rejecting the endless supply

of technological solutionism opens a space for reclaiming social justice and the real possibility of a just transition.

AI isn't inevitable but there's no going back to a pre-AI status quo, because our systems were already structured on injustice and heading for planetary burnout. The problem with AI isn't the way it's ruined democratic accountability and institutional stability, but that it amplifies the cruelties that were already built in to the order of things. AI's inability to manifest the claims made about it sheds an unforgiving light on the way the rest of our systems were already failing to deliver. While it may seem like an overwhelming proposition to say that we need systemic transformation, decomputing offers an entry point by asking how we determine sociotechnical forms that would iterate towards a fairer society. We should resist AI not simply because it is a harmful technology in its own right but because it's part of a nihilistic attempt to hold onto power by the same forces that created the crises in the first place. What AI shows us is not only that a reductive and preemptive epistemology is a poor foundation for a more caring world, but that the technopolitics of power will continue to produce mechanisms for defining who can be regarded as disposable. The real energy source behind the roll out of AI infrastructure isn't gas turbines or even fantasies about nuclear fusion, but fear. The techno-patriarchy everywhere fears the loss of unquestioned mastery, and AI is deployed as a way to build a moat of control under conditions of structural instability. Better to accelerate the burn than admit fragility or allow the rest of us to have a real say in the conditions of our own existence.

Decomputing isn't only a mode of technopolitical analysis but a call for constructive alternatives. As a prefigurative intervention, it tries to map paths to infrastructures of the common good that don't fall back into the same capitalist and patriarchal patterns. While the concepts and practices of decomputing aren't sufficient to challenge the totality of contemporary nihilism, they are one starting point for reconstructing systems that recognise our mutual vulnerability and interdependence. Challenging the way the abstract models of AI perpetuate forms of authoritarian social relationships leads us to question the structures that produce and promote them. AI is the contradiction that sheds light on many others, especially the divergence between claims to legitimacy by our existing systems and the actuality of destructive violence. Decomputing points to a post-sovereign technopolitics that rebuilds legitimacy through solidarity, mutual aid and the development of material mechanisms for situated survivability and sustainable ecological relations.

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